

Exposure to Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons from wood burning

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PAH Sampling tubes and sampling pumps

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Preface

My name is Dieter Pientka. I studied chemistry and I am a citizen scientist at Scapeler. I work on raising awareness that clean and healthy air is vital to life. My growing interest in air quality has led me to measure air quality with sensors for the past 15 years. During this journey, I have learned that human activities can have a significant impact on the local air quality. Private wood burning is such a dominant source of air pollution in local residential areas. Initially, I began to investigate the contribution of particulate matter from local wood stoves. This led to a large-scale study using the Met-One BAM1020 particulate matter monitor, resulting in a detailed report. I have always been particularly interested in Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons, abbreviated as PAHs. PAHs are unique and fascinating molecules but can also be very harmful to humans, animals, and the environment. There was a strong desire to conduct my own study into the exposure to PAHs emitted by private wood burning. The study became a reality thanks to the generous donations of many citizens. This report is another important step in raising awareness that heating our homes with a wood-burning stove is a bad choice for our health and the environment.

My name is Inge Everhardus. I have been working as a physician specialized in Public Health. A few years ago, my concern arose when municipalities started to advise residents to stop heating with natural gas but failed to issue warnings about the health risks associated with wood burning. Delving into the scientific literature on the health risks associated with wood burning, it became increasingly clear that these risks are greatly underestimated, also for ECO-design wood stoves. During my time that I was a board member of Stichting HoutrookVrij (Wood Smoke Free Foundation), it became obvious that people with (serious) health problems and odour nuisance were not being offered any protection. Raising awareness of this underestimated public health impact from wood burning is crucial. Therefore, I thought it is important to contribute to Dieter's report on the PAH measurements, by analysing the results, researching relevant scientific publications and writing in the corresponding sections in this paper.

Summary

This study investigated the (hyper)local human exposure to Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) in the outside air, emitted by nearby wood fired appliances in the living environment. During the winter season from 2024 to 2025, a total of 17 successful measurements of PAHs in the outside air were conducted at 13 different locations in the Netherlands. For this study the focus is on the 16 EPA-PAHs as defined by the Environmental Protection Agency (US-EPA). Special interest applies to Benzo[a]Pyrene and Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene which are the most carcinogenic PAHs as defined by both the US-EPA and the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). The sampling of PAHs is performed by use of a sampling pump in combination with a PDMS/Tenax absorption tube for a total sampling time of approximately 24 hours. This method has the important advantage that also the more volatile PAHs like Naphthalene are captured. The analysis of PAHs is performed by the Flemish Institute for Technological Research in Belgium (VITO).

The measurement of PAHs is performed in combination with the measurement of the concentration of particles ≤ 2.5 micrometer (μm) in size (PM_{2.5}) to identify the presence of wood smoke. PM_{2.5} is measured by use of the Plantower PMSA003 sensor. Very high (raw) peak values > 250 microgram/ m^3 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) were measured at various sampling locations, with the highest peak value of $1804 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ measured at the Sneek location. At location Sneek, also the highest average PM_{2.5} concentration of $118 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ is measured.

In general, a great variety in PAHs concentrations, but also in the PAHs compositions is observed among the 13 sampling locations. The highest concentrations of total PAHs are measured in Sneek, respectively $177 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ (ng/m^3) and $123 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ for two measurements on two different days. This location is highly exposed to wood smoke resulting in regularly very high PM_{2.5} peak values far above $250 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The lowest concentration of $0.5 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ total PAHs is measured for one experiment in Middelburg and is considered as the background concentration of 'clean air'. The highest concentration of an individual PAH is observed for Naphthalene in Sneek with a value of $119.6 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$. In general, Naphthalene shows also the highest average relative contribution to the total PAHs concentration with a value of 22.3%, followed by Fluorene with 11.3% and Anthracene with 9.0%.

The reported concentration of the carcinogenic Benzo[a]Pyrene varies between $<0.1 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ in Middelburg Zuidzijde and $1.27 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ in Schoorl. The average value of Benzo[a]Pyrene is $0.44 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ (16 measurements) and is 1.5 times higher than the average value for the winter season reported for a location of the Dutch national air quality monitoring network in Wijk aan Zee ($0.28 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$, 2024, 42 measurements). The location in Wijk aan Zee is 1 to 1,5 km north from the large industrial complex Tata Steel. Tata Steel is known for its PAHs emissions into the environment. The maximum value for Benzo[a]Pyrene reported in this study (Schoorl, $1.27 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$) is 1.7 times higher than the maximum value reported for Wijk aan Zee ($0.76 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$).

The reported concentration of Dibenz[ah]Anthracene, which is 2.4 times more carcinogenic as Benzo[a]Pyrene, varies between $<0.1 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ in Middelburg Zuidzijde and $5.22 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ in Vlissingen. The average value of Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene is $1.05 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ (16 measurements) and is 7.5 times higher than the average value for the winter season reported for Wijk aan Zee ($0.14 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$, 2024, 42 measurements). The maximum value for Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene reported in this study (Vlissingen, $5.22 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$) is 17 times higher than the maximum value reported for location Wijk aan Zee ($0.31 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$).

Investigation of the LML data for the whole year 2024 shows a seasonal effect with the highest values for November till April. The most obvious explanation for the seasonal effect would be private wood burning in nearby residential areas

One measurement at Schoorl is subjected to both the analysis of the 16 EPA-PAHs and the analysis of 10 of the most abundant Semi Volatile Organic Components (SVOC). The reported concentrations of the SVOC's are a factor 40 to 400 higher than the total PAHs concentration. The highest concentration of 25.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ is reported for 2,5-Cyclohexadiene-1,4-dione, 2,5-diphenyl-, a strong irritating quinone that can cause asthma symptoms.

Based on the results of this study, the concentration of the 16 EPA-PAHs in the outside air can reach a level of 350 times the concentration of clean air if active wood burning appliances are nearby. The concentration of Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene is for 50% of the measurements more than twice the concentration of Benzo[a]Pyrene. Although Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene is 2.4 times more carcinogenic than Benzo[a]Pyrene, it does not need to be registered under the 4 PRTR-PAHs in the EU and is not included in exceedances of the PAH standard. However, the US Department of Public Health and the US-EPA recommend considering the equivalent effects known of other carcinogenic PAHs. More research is requested including into the interactions that occur within the different PAH mixtures because it is shown that non carcinogenic low molecular weight PAHs can enhance the carcinogenicity of high molecular weight PAHs. Recent research shows that the 16 EPA-PAHs appear to represent only 1% of all PAH-derivatives formed during combustion processes, mainly wood and coal. The other 99% are equally toxic and 13 times more carcinogenic than Benzo[a]Pyrene at equal mass concentrations.

Therefore, the WHO warns that the current annual WHO-limit of 0.12 ng/m^3 Benzo[a]Pyrene as indicator substance probably does not provide sufficient protection to humans. The WHO indicates that for carcinogenic PAHs there is no safe threshold, so the lowest possible exposure should be aimed. The limit was calculated for the risk of lung cancer, not for all types of cancer and not for the oxidative effects from PAH such as cardiorespiratory diseases and developmental and behavioral disorders in children. Therefore, with respect for our health, both the WHO-limit and EU-limit (1 ng/m^3) looks to be outdated. In particular, wood burning is underestimated. According to European research, the oxidized PAH mixtures from private wood burning appear to be the main source of the oxidative potential of PM_{2.5} in Europe. The oxidative stress and (resulting) inflammatory reactions explain the cellular and DNA damage observed with PM_{2.5}.

This study did not show a clear relation between windspeed and PAHs concentration. Based on 17 measurements, the correlation coefficient is 0.105. One would expect that higher wind speeds would lead to higher dilution of the PAH concentration. However, due to local wind effects, such as the downdraft effect, a higher PAH concentration can even occur at higher wind speeds. The highest concentration of Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene in Vlissingen (5.22 ng/m^3) is measured with an average windspeed of 4 Bft. A high wind speed does not guarantee good air quality.

In many locations, wood is daily used as fuel to heat houses for a significant part of the year. It must be clearly understood that residential wood burning will cause a significant increase of the human exposure to PAHs in the outside air. This can lead to increased risk of human health damage. Recent British research conducted by Ricardo has shown that modern ECO-design wood stoves emit more PAHs and black carbon than older types of wood stoves and fireplaces. In the UK, the Ricardo report resulted in far-reaching consequences. The English Advertising Standards Authority has urged the English stove industry to stop advertising that modern ECO-design stoves significantly reduce harmful emissions. Let this be a valuable lesson in raising awareness that burning wood can never be clean and that the emissions have a huge impact on the local air quality. Good air quality is vital for our health, nature and climate.

Phasing out private wood burning should therefore be high on the political agenda.

Samenvatting

Deze studie onderzocht de (hyper)lokale blootstelling van mensen aan polycyclische aromatische koolwaterstoffen (PAK's) in de buitenlucht, afkomstig van nabijgelegen op hout gestookte toestellen in de woonomgeving. Gedurende het winterseizoen van 2024 tot 2025 werden in totaal 17 succesvolle metingen van PAK's in de buitenlucht uitgevoerd op 13 verschillende locaties in Nederland. Voor deze studie ligt de focus op de 16 EPA-PAK's zoals gedefinieerd door de Environmental Protection Agency (US-EPA). Bijzondere aandacht gaat uit naar Benzo[a]Pyreen en Dibenz[a,h]Antraceen, de meest kankerverwekkende PAK's volgens zowel de US-EPA als ook het International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). De bemonstering van PAK's werd uitgevoerd met behulp van een bemonsteringspomp in combinatie met een PDMS/Tenax-absorptiebuis gedurende een totale bemonsteringstijd van ongeveer 24 uur. Deze methode heeft als belangrijk voordeel dat ook de meer vluchtige PAK's zoals naftaleen worden gemeten. De analyse van PAK's werd uitgevoerd door het Vlaams Instituut voor Technologisch Onderzoek in België (VITO).

De meting van PAK's werd gecombineerd met de meting van de concentratie van deeltjes ≤ 2.5 micrometer (μm) (PM_{2.5}) om de aanwezigheid van houtrook te identificeren. PM_{2.5} werd gemeten met behulp van de Plantower PMSA003-sensor. Op verschillende meetlocaties werden zeer hoge (ruwe) piekwaarden van > 250 microgram/ m^3 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) gemeten, met de hoogste piekwaarde van $1804 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ op locatie Sneek. Op locatie Sneek werd ook de hoogste gemiddelde PM_{2.5}-concentratie van $118 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ gemeten.

Over het algemeen is een grote variatie in PAK-concentraties waargenomen, ook in de samenstelling van de PAK's tussen de 13 bemonsteringslocaties. De hoogste concentraties totale PAK's werden gemeten in Sneek, respectievelijk $177 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ (ng/m^3) en $123 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ tijdens metingen op twee verschillende dagen. Deze locatie is sterk blootgesteld aan houtrook, wat resulteert in regelmatig zeer hoge PM_{2.5}-piekwaarden van ruim boven de $250 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. De laagste concentratie totale PAK's van $0.5 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ werd gemeten tijdens één experiment in Middelburg en wordt beschouwd als de achtergrondconcentratie van 'schone lucht'. De hoogste concentratie van een individuele PAK werd gemeten voor naftaleen in Sneek met een concentratie van $119.6 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$. Over het algemeen vertoont naftaleen ook de hoogste gemiddelde relatieve bijdrage aan de totale PAK-concentratie met een waarde van 22.3%, gevolgd door fluoreen met 11.3% en antraceen met 9.0%.

De gemeten concentratie van de kankerverwekkende stof Benzo[a]Pyreen varieert tussen $<0.1 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ in Middelburg Zuidzijde en $1.27 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ in Schoorl. De gemiddelde concentratie van Benzo[a]Pyreen is $0.44 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ (16 metingen) en is 1.5 keer hoger dan de gemiddelde concentratie voor het winterseizoen die is gerapporteerd voor een locatie van het Nederlandse nationale luchtkwaliteitsmeetnetwerk (LML) in Wijk aan Zee ($0.28 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$, 2024, 42 metingen). De LML-locatie in Wijk aan Zee ligt 1 tot 1.5 km ten noorden van het grote industriële complex Tata Steel. Tata Steel staat bekend om de uitstoot van PAK's in het milieu. De maximale concentratie van $1.27 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ voor Benzo[a]Pyreen die in dit onderzoek in Schoorl is gemeten, is 1.7 keer hoger dan de maximale concentratie van $0.76 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ die voor locatie Wijk aan Zee is gerapporteerd.

De gemeten concentratie van Dibenz[a,h]Antraceen, dat 2.4 keer meer kankerverwekkend is dan Benzo[a]Pyreen, varieert tussen $<0.1 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ in Middelburg Zuidzijde en $5.22 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ in Vlissingen. De gemiddelde concentratie van Dibenz[a,h]Antraceen is $1.05 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$ (16 metingen) en is 7.5 keer hoger dan de gemiddelde concentratie voor het winterseizoen die is gerapporteerd voor de LML-locatie Wijk aan Zee ($0.14 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$, 2024, 42 metingen).

De maximale concentratie van 5.22 ng/m³ voor Dibenz[a,h]Antraceen die in deze studie is gemeten in Vlissingen, is 17 keer hoger dan de maximale concentratie van 0.31 ng/m³ die is gerapporteerd voor de locatie Wijk aan Zee. Onderzoek van de gerapporteerde LML-gegevens voor het gehele jaar 2024 toont een seizoen effect aan met de hoogste concentraties van november tot en met april. De meest voor de hand liggende verklaring voor het seizoen effect is het stoken van hout in nabijgelegen woonwijken.

Deze studie heeft geen duidelijk verband aangetoond tussen windsnelheid en PAK-concentratie. Op basis van 17 metingen is de correlatiecoëfficiënt 0.105. Men zou verwachten dat een hogere windsnelheid zou leiden tot een grotere verdunning van de PAK-concentratie. Door lokale windeffecten, zoals het downdraft effect, kan zelfs bij hogere windsnelheden een hoge PAK-concentratie voorkomen. De hoogste concentratie Dibenz[a,h]Antraceen in Vlissingen (5.22 ng/m³) werd gemeten bij een gemiddelde windsnelheid van 4 Beaufort. Een hoge windsnelheid garandeert dus geen goede luchtkwaliteit.

Eén meting in Schoorl werd uitgevoerd voor zowel de analyse van de 16 EPA-PAK's als de analyse van 10 van de meest voorkomende semi-vluchtige organische componenten (SVOC's). De gemeten concentraties van de SVOC's zijn 40 tot 400 keer hoger dan de totale PAK-concentratie. De hoogste concentratie 25.1 µg/m³ werd gemeten voor 2,5-cyclohexadien-1,4-dion, 2,5-difenylnon, een sterk irriterende chinon die astmaklachten kan veroorzaken.

Op basis van de resultaten van dit onderzoek kan de concentratie 16 EPA-PAK's in de buitenlucht een niveau bereiken dat 350 keer hoger is dan de concentratie in schone lucht, als er in de buurt actieve houtkachels aanwezig zijn. De concentratie Dibenz[a,h]Antraceen is bij 50% van de metingen meer dan twee keer zo hoog als de concentratie Benzo[a]Pyreen. Dibenz[a,h]Antraceen is 2.4 keer zo kankerverwekkend, maar hoeft niet te worden geregistreerd onder de 4 PRTR-PAK's in de EU en wordt niet meegerekend voor overschrijding van de PAK-norm. Het Amerikaanse ministerie van Volksgezondheid en de Amerikaanse EPA adviseren daarentegen wel om rekening te houden met de equivalente effecten van andere bekende kankerverwekkende PAK's. Meer onderzoek is nodig, zoals naar de onderlinge interacties in PAK-mengsels. Uit onderzoek is gebleken dat niet-kankerverwekkende PAK's met laagmoleculair gewicht de kankerverwekkende werking van PAK's met hoogmoleculair gewicht kunnen versterken. Recent onderzoek laat zien dat de 16 EPA-PAK's slechts 1% vertegenwoordigen van alle PAK-derivaten die tijdens verbrandingsprocessen ontstaan, van voornamelijk hout en steenkool. De overige 99% zijn even toxisch en 13 keer zo kankerverwekkend als Benzo[a]Pyreen bij dezelfde massa concentraties.

De WHO waarschuwde al eerder dat de huidige WHO-limiet met 0.12 ng/m³ Benzo[a]Pyreen als indicatorstof waarschijnlijk onvoldoende bescherming biedt. Volgens de WHO bestaat er voor de kankerverwekkende PAK's geen drempelwaarde en moet er gestreefd worden naar de laagst mogelijke blootstelling. Daarnaast geeft de WHO aan dat de WHO-limiet is berekend op basis van het risico op longkanker, niet op alle andere vormen van kanker die kunnen ontstaan, noch op de oxidatieve effecten van PAK's zoals hart- en vaatziekten, longaandoeningen en ontwikkelings- en gedragsstoornissen bij kinderen. Met het oog op onze gezondheid lijken dus zowel de WHO-limiet als de EU-limiet (1 ng/m³) achterhaald. Met name van particuliere houtstook wordt de impact onderschat. Volgens Europese wetenschappers zijn namelijk de geoxideerde PAK-mengsels uit particuliere houtstook de belangrijkste bron van het oxidatieve potentieel in het PM2.5 in Europa. De oxidatieve stress en (veroorzaakte) ontstekingsreacties brengen schade toe aan afweer- en weefselcellen en aan DNA zoals die worden gezien als gevolg van PM2.5.

Op veel plaatsen wordt hout dagelijks gebruikt als brandstof om huizen te verwarmen gedurende een aanzienlijk deel van het jaar. Het is van groot belang te realiseren dat het stoken van hout in woningen de blootstelling van de mens aan PAK's in de buitenlucht aanzienlijk doet toenemen. Dit leidt tot een verhoogd risico op gezondheidsschade.

Recent Brits onderzoek van de Ricardo-groep heeft aangetoond dat moderne ECO-design houtkachels meer PAK's en black carbon (roet) uitstoten dan oude typen houtkachels en open haarden. In het Verenigd Koninkrijk heeft het Ricardo-rapport verstrekkende gevolgen gehad. De Engelse reclameautoriteit (ASA) heeft de Engelse kachelindustrie (SIA) opgeroepen te stoppen met het uiten van reclame dat moderne ECO-design houtkachels de schadelijke uitstoot aanzienlijk verminderen. Laat dit een waardevolle les zijn om het bewustzijn te vergroten dat het stoken van hout nooit schoon kan zijn en dat de uitstoot een enorme impact heeft op de lokale luchtkwaliteit. Een goede luchtkwaliteit is essentieel voor onze gezondheid, de natuur en het klimaat.

Uitfasering van particuliere houtstook zou daarom hoog op de politieke agenda moeten staan.

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1 Introduction

Wood smoke pollution has been a sensitive issue for many years, causing significant air pollution and human suffering. Wood smoke contains many harmful substances, including toxic and even carcinogenic species. A significant part of these toxic and carcinogenic species consists of PAHs and oxidized PAHs.

PAHs are a group of organic compounds composed of aromatic rings, without hetero atoms or functional groups in their molecular structure. PAHs consists of only carbon and hydrogen atoms. PAHs are hydrophobic and are persistent in the environment. PAHs are known for their toxicity to humans and animals. They can be irritating for eyes, skin and mucous membranes, but several PAHs have carcinogenic properties. In addition, PAHs can react with oxygen and especially the oxidized PAHs cause oxidative damage to human cells and DNA. PAHs are considered as substances of very high concern. The most well-known toxic PAHs are Benzo[a]Pyrene and Dibenz[ah]Anthracene. The International Agency for Research on Cancer ([IARC¹](https://monographs.iarc.fr/)) has determined that Benzo[a]Pyrene is carcinogenic to humans and animals and is currently classified in Group 1 with the highest burden of proof. The US Department of Public Health describe in their guidelines that Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene is 2.4 times more carcinogenic than Benzo[a]Pyrene ([ATSDR²](https://www.atsdr.cdc.gov/pha-guidance/resources/ATSDR-PAH-Guidance-508.pdf) page 5 & 6). The recommendation is to consider other carcinogenic EPA-PAHs in addition to the carcinogenicity of Benzo[a]Pyrene when calculating the cancer risk of PAH mixtures. This should be done by multiplying the PAH concentration by the Potency Equivalency Factor (PEF) and adding this to Benzo[a]Pyrene. The PEFs of Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene (2.4), Benzo[a]Pyrene (1) and other PAHs are listed in [ATSDR²](https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/350636/9789289056533-eng.pdf), see table 1.

The US-EPA has defined a standard set of 16 PAHs as priority pollutants, used as a standard set to assess the potential health risks of exposure to PAHs and are measured in environmental conditions such as food, water, soil and air. Four of the 16 EPA-PAHs belong to the so-called 'PRTR (Pollutant Release and Transfer Register) PAHs'. The 4 PRTR PAHs are Benzo[a]Pyrene, Benzo[b]Fluoranthene, Benzo[k]Fluoranthene, and Indeno[1,2,3-cd]Pyrene. This group of four specific PAHs are subjected to reporting under the EU PRTR Regulations. However, the strong carcinogenic Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene is not included.

The legal European limit value for the annual average concentration of Benzo[a]Pyrene in air is 1 ng/m³ (1 nanogram/m³). Benzo[a]Pyrene is used as an indicator for the existence of PAHs. Currently, it is still a target that must be strived for, but in 2030 it will become a real limit value and enforcement will be mandatory. The PAH results of this study cannot be compared with the legal EU limit because this requires an average annual value.

According to the [WHO³](https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/350636/9789289056533-eng.pdf) there is no safe threshold for carcinogenic PAHs, so the lowest possible exposure should be aimed. The WHO warns that the current WHO-limit (an annual average of 0.12 ng Benzo[a]Pyrene/m³) probably does not provide sufficient protection against other carcinogenic PAH-derivates, neither against other types of cancer than lung cancer and neither against oxidative effects such as cardiorespiratory diseases and developmental- and behavioural disorders in children. Therefore, with respect for our health, the EU-limit but also the WHO limit looks to be outdated.

1 <https://monographs.iarc.fr/>

2 <https://www.atsdr.cdc.gov/pha-guidance/resources/ATSDR-PAH-Guidance-508.pdf>

3 <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/350636/9789289056533-eng.pdf> (page vii)

In particular, the impact of private wood burning is underestimated. The oxidized PAH mixtures in wood smoke appear to be the most important source of the oxidation potential in PM_{2.5} in Europe, according to European and Hungarian research. Oxidative stress and the (resulting) inflammatory reactions explain the cellular and DNA damage observed with PM_{2.5}.

PAHs primarily originate from combustion of organic matter and exposure to high heat or pressure. In addition to wood combustion, emission of PAHs can also occur from anthropogenic sources like smoking, cooking, vehicle use and industrial processes and occur from naturally sources like forest fires and volcano eruptions. The formation of PAHs involves complex chemical reactions and the release of free radicals that lead to the formation of fused aromatic rings. Oxidized PAHs^{4,5} are more reactive as radicals due to the additional oxide molecules. The Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) calculates every year the emission of pollutants to the air caused by Dutch sources. Domestic wood burning in the Netherlands is accountable for 62.5% (2023)⁶ of the total emission of Benzo[a]Pyrene to the air. These emissions come from 12.6%⁷ of households that (partly) heat their homes with wood.

When outside wood burning, Easter fires, bonfires and house fires caused by wood burning are included, the contribution grows to 73.2%. This contribution is more than industry, traffic and transport together. What makes things even worse is that most of the wood fired appliances are situated within the residential environment, where people live close to each other.

Recent British research conducted by Ricardo⁸ has shown that modern ECO-design wood stoves emit more PAHs and black carbon than old types of wood stoves and fireplaces. In the UK, the Ricardo report has had far-reaching consequences. The English Advertising Standards Authority (ASA⁹) has urged the English stove industry (SIA) to stop advertising that modern ECO-design stoves significantly reduce harmful emissions. The Guardian⁹ has reported about ASA's ruling.

This study focuses on the (hyper)local human exposure to the 16 EPA-PAHs in the outside air, caused by nearby wood fired appliances in the living environment. Many innocent citizens suffer from wood smoke from nearby or neighbour's wood stove and are being exposed to wood smoke containing high levels of PAHs. The exposure will be the highest in the vicinity of the wood burner's house. During this study, the concentration of PAHs in outside air was measured to investigate to what level human exposure can be expected. From an awareness perspective, it is important to realize that exposure to PAHs from nearby wood stoves will depend on the frequency of wood stove use. When citizens heat their house with a wood stove, they will be using it almost daily in the cold season. Therefore, exposure to PAHs will be higher during a significant part of the year.

This study was conducted by the author and volunteers in collaboration with the specialized laboratory VITO (Flemish Institute for Technological Research, Mol, Belgium). The primary results and explanations of the PAHs analysis are documented in a VITO report with reference 2025/EI/R/3426, June 2025, authors: Borislav Lazarov, Martine Van Poppel and Nic Moonen. Permission has been granted by VITO to use the primary analysis results in this report.

4 <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-020-2902-8>

5 <https://acp.copernicus.org/articles/23/14255/2023/>

6 <https://www.rivm.nl/houtrook/bijdrage-houtstook-aan-uitstoot-en-luchtkwaliteit> (figure 3)

7 <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/nieuws/2024/06/bijna-1-op-de-3-huishoudens-met-haard-of-kachel-stookte-meer-in-2023>

8 https://naei.energysecurity.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2025-02/Ricardo%20EFDSF%20Report_WP3_Issue4_FINAL_v2.pdf ECO-design wood stoves emit more PAH (page 60). Measurements were performed with nominal wood use (1,2 kg, page 6). According to BeReal, wood stoves operate less under nominal conditions. 2 kg wood (SINTEF/RISE, page 6) emits twice as much PM/GJ than 1.2 kg wood. That's why Ricardo generally measures lower emissions compared to EMEP

9 <https://www.asa.org.uk/rulings/stove-industry-alliance-ltd-a25-1292745-stove-industry-alliance-ltd.html> + <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2025/nov/06/misleading-uk-adverts-for-very-low-emission-wood-burning-stoves-banned>

2 Experimental

The sampling and analysis of PAHs in air is performed in three steps: sampling, thermal desorption and analysis using a combination of gas chromatography and mass spectrometry (GC/MS). The complete detailed procedure is prescribed in the [article¹⁰](#) 'Optimization steps of an innovative air sampling method for semi volatile organic compounds', published by Borislav Lazarov, Rudi Swinnen, Maarten Spruyt, Eddy Goelen, Marianne Stranger, Gilbert Desmet and Eric Wauters.

2.1 Sampling tubes

During the sampling, the PAHs are 'trapped' on a specially designed stainless-steel tube ([Markes International Ltd¹¹](#)), 9 cm length, 6.53 mm outer diameter and 5 mm inner diameter filled with Poly-Di-Methyl-Siloxane/Tenax sorbent material (figure 1), suitable for thermal desorption.

Figure 1: PDMS/Tenax absorption tube

Poly-Di-Methyl-Siloxane is used as a carrier for the Tenax absorption component. Tenax is the trademark of the absorption material Poly-(2,6-diphenylphenylene oxide); an oxidized polymer of 2,6-diphenylphenol. The sampling tubes have been preconditioned and delivered by VITO. Preconditioning is performed by thermal cleaning under a nitrogen flow at 300 °C for 60 minutes and finally properly sealed with brass end caps.

2.2 Thermal Desorption

After receiving the sampled tubes at VITO, the tubes were stored under a nitrogen atmosphere. Thermal desorption (TD100 Thermal desorber, Markes International Ltd) of the sampling tubes was carried out at 300 °C with a flow rate of 20 mL/min for 12 min, followed by focussing on a 10°C cold trap. The Thermal desorber system control was performed using Thermal Desorber System Control Program version 4.4.1 (Markes International Ltd.).

2.3 GC/MS analysis

The thermal desorption and analysis of the sample tubes were performed in the laboratory at VITO. The analysis of the 16 EPA-PAHs (see figure 2) was performed using a GC/MS system operating in Selected Ion Monitoring (SIM) mode. Each of the target PAH components was detected using a combination of the GC retention time and a qualifier MS ion fragment. The amount of the target compounds in the samples is calculated using the method of external standard calibration curve.

10 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1352231013005906>

11 <https://markes.com/>

The concentration of PAHs in air was calculated considering the volume of the sampled air for each of the samples. The sampling technique with PDMS/Tenax tubes collects both gas phase as well as particulate matter. The PDMS/Tenax method measures higher Naphthalene values compared to the EU-method and the total PAH is not equivalent with the EU-method. Particularly the heavy PAHs with high boiling points absorb on the particulate matter in air. Refer to table 1 for the properties of the 16 EPA-PAHs. The total amount of PAHs, analyzed with this method, is the combination of the PAHs present in the gas phase and the PAHs absorbed on particulate matter.

Figure 2: The 16 EPA-PAHs target components of this study

The limit of detection (LOD) is 0.1 ng/m³ for all PAHs. The LOD is valid for a total sampling volume of 480 liter of air. The reproducibility is 10% for all PAHs.

Besides the determination of the 16 EPA-PAHs, the method can also be used to analyse other semi-volatile organic compounds (SVOC) in air. For one of the sampled tubes, it was chosen to expand the analysis of the 16 EPA-PAHs with the MS identification of the 10 most abundant peaks present in the chromatogram. The extra peaks were identified by comparing the obtained MS spectrum with a NIST23 MS library. For this analysis a positive identification was considered for the compound with the highest qualification factor calculated from the MS library. Only components with qualification factors above 80 were considered for this analysis. The concentrations of these SVOC components were expressed as the Naphthalene Equivalent, i.e. the concentrations are calculated using the response factor of Naphthalene.

PAH	Nr in figure 2	Boiling Point (°C)	IARC Class#	PEF##
Naphthalene	1	218	2B	na
Acenaphthylene	2	280	3	na
Acenaphthene	3	279	3	na
Fluorene	4	295	3	na
Phenanthrene	5	332	3	na
Anthracene	6	340	3	na
Fluoranthene	7	375	3	na
Pyrene	8	404	3	na
Benzo[a]Anthracene	9	438	2B	0.1
Chrysene	10	448	2B	0.01
Benzo[b]Fluoranthene	11	481	2B	0.1
Benzo[k]Fluoranthene	12	480	2B	0.1
Benzo[a]Pyrene	13	495	1	1.0
Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene	14	524	2A	2.4
Benzo[g,h,i]Perylene	15	550	3	na
Indeno[1,2,3-cd]Pyrene	16	536	2B	0.1

Table 1: Properties of the 16 EPA-PAHs

#: The IARC Classification codes give an assessment of the strength of the evidence for carcinogenicity, whereby:

- 1 : Carcinogenic to humans with the highest burden of proof
- 2A : Probably carcinogenic to humans
- 2B : Possibly carcinogenic to humans
- 3 : Not classifiable as to its carcinogenicity to humans

##: The Potency Equivalency Factor. In 2022, the US Department of Public Health Service ([ATSDR²](#)) developed a guideline using data from the US EPA and the Californian EPA to calculate the relative carcinogenicity of EPA-PAHs compared to Benzo[a]Pyrene. The relative carcinogenicity is expressed as the Potency Equivalency Factor (PEF). This allows the concentration of the individual carcinogenic EPA-PAHs to be multiplied by the corresponding PEF and then added to the concentration of Benzo[a]Pyrene to determine the risk of cancer of various PAH mixtures. Scientists from the University of Cincinnati Public Health Department believe more research is necessary into administration methods and testing on human cells and organoids without animal testing. Furthermore, it applies that PAHs show different carcinogenic mechanisms and individual PAHs interact with each other in PAH mixtures. [German- and American¹²](#) research showed that non carcinogenic low molecular weight PAHs can enhance the carcinogenicity of high molecular weight PAHs. German scientists published an [article¹³](#) showing that non-EPA PAHs accounted for 69%-95% of the carcinogenicity of 59 PAHs reported.

In the EU, Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene does not need to be registered under the 4 PRTR PAH standard. This raises the question whether the 4 PRTR standard is suitable for determining exposure to PAHs from wood burning. Because the PEF of Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene is 2.4 times higher than that of Benzo[a]Pyrene, it was decided to pay specific attention to both Benzo[a]Pyrene and Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene during the analysis of the measurement results of this study.

12 <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5866845/>

13 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0045653518303588?via%3Dihub>

3 Sampling locations & procedure

The selected sampling locations are locations with wood smoke nuisance. Different locations, spread across the Netherlands are chosen. As result, there are differences in environment, weather conditions, type of wood fired appliances, wood burner's behavior and type of wood. To omit long traveling distances, the chosen locations are on the westside of the Netherlands. For approximately 50% of the locations the residents were asked if they would like to participate and cooperate with the project, because it was known there was significant wood smoke present on that location. The other locations were chosen based on responses on a call raised via social media. At all selected locations there is an active particulate matter (PM) sensor installed, measuring the outside air quality (PM1, PM2.5 and PM10). The PM2.5 readings were used to identify the presence of wood smoke during the PAHs sampling. All sensors at the selected locations are part of the Scapeler¹⁴ network. The Scapeler sensor network consists of approximately 125 Aprisensor¹⁵ kits and the locations are spread across The Netherlands, Belgium with some kits in Switzerland and one in Japan. For this study, the following locations have been selected: Ameide, Barneveld, Ede, Groet, Middelburg, Nunspeet, Purmerend, Schoorl, 's-Gravenpolder, Sneek, Vlissingen, Warmenhuizen and Zoetermeer. The sample locations are presented in figure 3.

Figure 3: PAHs sample locations in the Netherlands

14 <https://dataportaal.openiod.org/dashboard>

15 <https://www.scapeler.com/index.php/aprisensor/>

A brief description of the sampling locations is given below. Due to privacy statements, only the place of residence is mentioned. The number of citizens is mentioned between hooks.

- Ameide : A village very close to the river Lek. Sampling location is on the border of the village where direct neighbors use a wood stove to heat their house. Other wood stoves are also active, mainly in southeast to southwest directions (3.200).
- Barneveld : A town in the center of The Netherlands. Sampling location in a suburb where several wood stoves are active in all wind directions, but mainly from the southeast (63.512).
- Ede : A town in the center of The Netherlands. Sampling location in a suburb where direct neighbors use a wood stove to heat their house. Other wood stoves are active, mainly in north and west directions (124.214).
- Groet : A small village very close to the North Sea coast. Sampling location in the village where neighbors use a wood stove to heat their house. Other wood stoves are also active in all directions (1.525).
- Middelburg : A town close to the Westerschelde and the North Sea coast. Sampling location in a suburb where two direct neighbors next to each other use a wood stove to heat their house. Other wood stoves are active in all wind directions (50.352).
- Nunspeet : A town close to Veluwemeer. Sampling location in a suburb where several wood stoves are active, mainly in west and south directions (29.677).
- Purmerend : A town close to Markermeer. Sampling location in the middle of the city. Wood stoves are active on all wind directions (95.912).
- Schoorl : A village close to the North Sea coast and dunes. Sampling location on the border of the village where two direct neighbors use a wood stove to heat their house. Many other wood stoves are active in all wind directions, but mainly south from the location. In February 2009 the concentration of wood smoke in a residential area in Schoorl was investigated by [ECN¹⁶](#) over a period of three weeks. The aim was to assess the effect of local particulate matter emissions, caused by heating with wood stoves in this area (4.685).
- sGravenpolder: A village close to The Westerschelde. Sampling location is in the middle of the village where two direct neighbors use a wood stove to heat their house. Many wood stoves are active on all wind directions (4.635).
- Sneek : A town in the north of The Netherlands, east of the IJsselmeer. Sampling location in the middle of the city. There is a nearby wood stove situated at direct neighbors (35.130).
- Vlissingen : A town on the coast of The Westerschelde. Sampling location with active wood stoves in mainly south and north directions (45.755).
- Warmenhuizen: A village close to Schoorl and Groet. Sampling location is on the border of the village. A few very active wood stoves on west wind directions within 50 meters (6.390).
- Zoetermeer : A town close to The Hague and Rotterdam. Sampling location on the border of a suburb in the city. Many wood stoves are active in mainly north to east wind directions (130.647).

The sampling procedure and supplies have been provided by VITO. The sampling is performed by the author and volunteers in collaboration with the author. For the sampling conditions, the author was personally instructed by VITO. It was chosen to perform the sampling by the author and volunteers to limit the costs for this study. The sampling setup consists of a sampling pump, a steel sampling Tenax tube and silicon hoses. The sampling setup was chosen on a representative side of the house at a height between 0.5 and 2.0 meters ("nose height"). The measurements were explicitly not performed at a short distance from the outlet of the chimney, because this would be outside the scope of the study. An example of the typical setup is given in figure 4.

Figure 4: Example of the typical sampling setup

The outside air is sampled for 24 +/- 3 hours with a constant flow of approximately 300 ml/min using a calibrated constant-flow sampling pump (GSA SG350, GSA Messgerätebau, Germany), connected to the steel sampling tube via a silicone hose. The sampling tube is connected to the silicone hose. A special groove at the end of the tube indicates the side where the air flows into the tube. This construction is important for a successful trapping of the PAHs by the sorbent. The sampling tube must also be aligned vertically such rain will not enter the sampling tube. After sampling, the tubes were firmly closed by the brass end caps and stored at 4°C for a maximum period of three weeks. The sampled tubes were shipped to VITO by registered mail.

Information about the sampling conditions, location, sampling pump and sampling tube was recorded by use of a special measurement form. The template of this form is given in Appendix 1.

The following information is recorded on the measurement form:

- Brief description of the sampling location
- Date and time of sampling start and end
- Information about photos taken of the sampling setup

- Sampling pump identification number (important for the flow)
- Sampling tube identification number
- Notification of situations that could have impact on the measurement

The measurement forms including photos were essential information for VITO to assess the quality of the sampling setup and active sampling and to calculate the PAH concentrations.

4 Results & Discussion

This study focuses on the (hyper)local human exposure to PAHs in the outside air, caused by nearby inhouse wood fired appliances. A neighbour's wood stove will cause hyperlocal emission of wood smoke containing PAHs and the human exposure will be the highest in the vicinity of the wood burner's house. Due to downdraft effects, high concentrations of wood smoke can occur on a specific side of a house when the wind blows perpendicularly over the edge of the roof. The wood smoke can remain on that side of the house for a longer time and will not be blown away. During this study, the concentration of PAHs in outside air was measured to investigate to what level human exposure can be expected. The type of wood fired appliances is not investigated in this study, in many cases this information will not be available.

Besides PAHs, wood smoke contains high levels of PM2.5. PM-sensors were used to measure the PM2.5 concentration in the outside air during the PAHs sampling. The PM2.5 sensors were collocated with the PAHs measurement setup. For this study the Plantower¹⁷ PMSA003 is used, because this sensor was available on all sampling locations. The PMSA003 shows high sensitivity to wood smoke which is important to detect wood smoke events. The data of the PMSA003 sensors must be seen as an approximation of the true values. The PM2.5 data is not corrected for the relative humidity of the air.

4.1 Sampling conditions and meteorology

The total sampling time for most locations was 24 +/- 3 hours except for 's-Gravenpolder and Zoetermeer. In 's-Gravenpolder the sampling times were shorter, because the expensive sampling pump could not be protected from being stolen. For Nunspeet and Zoetermeer the sampling time was divided into two or three sub-sessions due to absence of wood smoke. In 's-Gravenpolder three sampling experiments (Exp.) were performed and in Groet, Middelburg, Nunspeet, Schoorl and Sneek two sampling experiments were performed. The measurements were performed if the smell of wood smoke was clearly noticeable or if wood burning appliances were active nearby. One measurement was performed as background, in that case there was no wood smoke present. The presence of wood smoke is checked by use of PM2.5 sensors.

Information about the sampling conditions and meteorological parameters is given in table 2.

Information about the meteorological parameters during the PAHs sampling is obtained from the Royal Dutch Meteorological Institute (KNMI) website. For every sampling location the nearest KNMI reference station is chosen to download the meteorological data. It is assumed the KNMI reference stations are representative for the meteorology on the sampling locations. The KNMI stations are given in table 3 inclusive the direct distance to the sampling location.

17 https://plantower.com/en/products_33/77.html

Sampling location	Location Code	Exp. nr	Tube ID	Sampling Dates	Total Sampling Time	Ses sions	T °C	RH %	WS (Bft)
Ameide	AME	1	171098	12/13-02-25	26h:55min	1	2	90	2
Barneveld	BNV	1	171096	26/27-01-25	24h:00min	1	7	80	4
Ede	EDE	1	227685	25/26-01-25	25h:32min	1	4	95	2
Groet	GRT1	1	171094	7/8-02-25	24h:00min	1	3	75	4
	GRT2	2	227670	19/20-02-25	26h:00min	1	1	65	3
Middelburg	MBG_Z	1	227665	22/23-12-24	20h:10min	1	7	70	6
	MBG_N	2	227663	22/23-12-24	20h:00min	1	7	70	6
Nunspeet	NUN1	1	171095	22/23-02-25	25h:06min	1	9	90	4
	NUN2	2	171097	25/26/27-02-25	25h:11min	3	6	80	3
Purmerend	PUR	1	171093	13/14-01-25	27h:00min	1	2	90	3
Schoorl	SCH1	1	227662	16/17-01-25	24h:23min	1	2	98#	2
	SCH2	2	227661	21/22-01-25	25h:15min	1	1	95	2
's-Gravenpolder	SGP1	1	227674	1/2-12-24	14h:30min	1	6	80	3
	SGP2	2	227673	3-12-24	13h:47min	1	5	80	2
	SGP3	3	171100	2/3-01-25	15h:10min	1	2	85	3
Sneek	SNK1	1	227671	17/18-01-25	24h:13min	1	-1	99#	2
	SNK2	2	171092	20/21-01-25	24h:00min	1	1	95	3
Vlissingen	VLS	1	227669	19/20-02-25	25h:38min	1	3	75	4
Warmenhuizen	WHZ	1	171091	30/31-01-25	27h:30min	1	3	90	2
Zoetermeer	ZOE	1	227666	25/26/27-02-25	16h:27min	3	6	80	4

Table 2: Sampling conditions and meteorological parameters for all sampling locations

: fog was present during the total sampling time

Location Code : Sampling location code

Exp. Nr : Experiment number

Tube ID : Tenax tube identification number

Total Sampling Time : The total sampling time in hours and minutes

T : The average temperature during the sampling experiment in °C

RH : The average relative humidity during the sampling experiment in %

WS : The average wind speed during the sampling experiment in Bft

The variations in meteorological conditions are normal for winter weather in the Netherlands. No sampling was conducted on windless days.

Sampling location	KNMI station	Direct distance (km)
Ameide	Cabauw	3
Barneveld	De Bilt	28
Ede	Deelen	16
Groet	Berkhout	23
Middelburg	Vlissingen	8
Nunspeet	Lelystad	28
Purmerend	Berkhout	15
Schoorl	Berkhout	20
's-Gravenpolder	Wilhelminadorp	8
Sneek	Leeuwarden	21
Vlissingen	Vlissingen	3
Warmenhuizen	Berkhout	19
Zoetermeer	Voorschoten	8

Table 3: KNMI reference stations

4.2 Investigation of the PAHs- and PM2.5 results

The primary PAH data reported by VITO is given in Appendix 2. The total PAHs concentration is the sum of all individual reported PAH concentrations. In figure 5 the total PAHs concentration is given for all sampling locations, except for Nunspeet and Zoetermeer. For Nunspeet and Zoetermeer the PAHs analysis at VITO was not successful and the results could not be reported. Due to transportation delays by the parcel service, the samples from Vlissingen and Groet were delivered to VITO four weeks after sampling. This extended transportation period should be taken into consideration when interpreting the results from Groet and Vlissingen. During the four weeks of transportation without cooling, light boiling PAHs could escape from the sampling tube. Hence, the reported values could be an underestimation of the true values.

The major source of PAHs during the sampling will be nearby wood fired appliances, but wood fired appliances on longer distances from the sampling location will contribute too. In general, due to dilution, the contribution of wood fired appliances over a longer distance will be lower than appliances close by. Another source of PAHs is traffic. Most sampling locations are not near traffic routes. However, the sampling locations in Purmerend, Sneek and Zoetermeer are situated in towns with more traffic. Fresh air without the smell of wood smoke and without significant PM2.5 registrations is considered as the background in this study. However, the background can still contain a significant concentration of PAHs, emitted by sources over a (very) long distance. In general, on calm and cold winter days with easterly winds, PAHs originated in Germany or Belgium can be transported to the Netherlands and will be present in the background. On mild and windy winter days with westerly winds, in general, the background will be lower in PAHs (VMM¹⁸).

Figure 5: The total PAHs concentration for all sampling locations

It is obvious there are large differences in the total PAHs concentration between the different locations. The lowest total PAHs concentration of 0.5 ng/m³ is reported for Middelburg Zuidzijde_227665 (MBG_Z). This sample could be considered as a background analysis. The motivation will be explained in more detail in section 4.5.5. The background presents the total PAHs concentration that can be expected for 'clean air'. The highest total PAHs concentrations of 176.7 ng/m³ and 122.0 ng/m³ are reported for respectively Sneek_1 and Sneek_2. This location is highly exposed to wood smoke.

It should be noted that the 16 EPA-PAHs represent only a very small portion of the total amount of PAHs. A Chinese research article (Zhong, 8-2019¹⁹) reports that the 16 EPA-PAHs represent approximately 1% of all PAHs derivatives from combustion processes. Another more recent Chinese article (Yao, 2024²⁰) reports that the other 99% of the PAHs derivatives show to be as toxic as Benzo[a]Pyrene and show 13 times more carcinogenic properties. Particularly PAH derivatives emitted by residential coal- and wood combustion are the most damaging to health.

For all individual sampling locations, the breakdown of the total PAHs concentrations into the individual PAH components is given in figure 6.

19 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1352231019302845>

20 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0048969724077891>

Figure 6: PAHs breakdown for all sampling locations

The following observations can be derived from figure 6:

1. The concentration of the strong carcinogenic Benzo[a]Pyrene is between 0.14 ng/m³ for Purmerend and 1.27 ng/m³ for Schoorl_2.
2. The concentration of the stronger carcinogen Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene is for 50% of the measurements more than twice the concentration of Benzo[a]Pyrene. The concentration varies from 0.11 ng/m³ at Ameide to 5.22 ng/m³ at Vlissingen.
3. The highest concentrations of Naphthalene are reported for Sneek_1, Sneek_2, Ameide and Ede. For Ameide and Ede the other PAHs are much lower in concentration.
4. The highest concentrations of Acenaphthene are reported for Sneek_2, Schoorl_2 and Vlissingen.
5. The highest concentrations of Phenanthrene and Anthracene are reported for Sneek_2
6. Anthracene is the only PAH reported for all sampling locations and all experiments.
7. All 16 PAHs are reported for Sneek_2 and Schoorl_2.
8. The breakdown profiles of Sneek_1 and Sneek_2 are not similar, Sneek_1 shows higher levels for the low boiling PAHs, while Sneek_2 shows higher levels for the high boiling PAHs. During the measurements in Sneek, the wood smoke came from the same wood stove(s), but probably not the same wood was used or different burning conditions.
9. The breakdown profiles of Schoorl_1 and Schoorl_2 are also not similar. Naphthalene, Acenaphthylene and Acenaphthene is not present in the profile of exp1. During the measurements in Schoorl, the wood smoke came from the same wood stove(s), but probably different kinds of wood were burned or different burning conditions.
10. The PAHs breakdown of Sneek_2 and Schoorl_2 are almost identical; the only difference is the concentration of Naphthalene which is much higher for Sneek_2.
11. The highest concentrations of the three most high boiling PAHs are reported for Vlissingen. There is no clear explanation for this behaviour.
12. The lowest PAHs concentration (PAHs total = 0.5 ng/m³) is reported for MBG_Z which is considered as the background level of clean air.

If all observations are summarized, the overall conclusion is, that among the different sampling locations there is a large variety in the PAHs concentration levels, but also a large variety in the PAHs breakdown profiles. In section 4.5 the specific PAHs breakdown for every sampling location will be discussed. The results of figure 6 can be compared with a similar kind of study reported in [Flandres²¹](#) in 2021. The measurement of PAHs was part of the Flandres study, and the same method was used for the sampling and analysis. In general, the PAHs results of the Flandres study are in line with the results of this study. The reported values for Naphthalene in the Flandres study are much higher than the other PAHs which is also observed for this study (inherent to the method used). The relevance of the PAHs concentrations given in figure 6 can be assessed by comparing with independent measurements on other locations. Therefore, the values of the two most harmful PAHs Benzo[a]Pyrene and Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene are compared with the 24 hours measurements available from the Dutch national air quality monitoring network ([LML²²](#)).

21 <https://www.departementzorg.be/nl/publicatie/interventiestudie-van-een-traditioneel-naar-een-bewust-beter-gebruik-van-houtkachels-samenvatting>

22 <https://www.luchtmeetnet.nl/>

At three LML-locations the measurement of PAHs is performed on a regularly basis:

1. De Zilk-Vogelaarsdreef : rural background location (LML-code 10444)
2. Rotterdam-Schiedamse Vest : urban location with high traffic (LML-code 10418)
3. Wijk aan Zee-De Banjaert : industrial location (LML-code 49553)

LML location De Zilk-Vogelaarsdreef is situated in dunes with forest areas and near bulb fields with no significant sources of PAHs nearby. LML location Rotterdam-Schiedamse Vest is situated along a road in a densely populated area with mainly high-rise buildings and traffic as a source of PAHs. LML-location 'Wijk aan Zee-De Banjaert' is 1 to 1.5 km north from the large Tata Steel industrial complex. Tata Steel is well known as an important industrial source of PAHs emissions and many citizens in the surrounding villages are concerned about their health. With predominantly south to west wind directions, it can be assumed that for most of the year Tata Steel's PAH emissions are also measured at the LML location Wijk aan Zee.

The LML-method involves analysis of PAHs present on PM10 (Particulate Matter $\leq 10\mu\text{m}$) aerosol material collected on a special glass fibre filter. It must be noted that the LML-method is different from the method used in this study. Besides other PAHs, Benzo[a]Pyrene and Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene are also measured with the LML-method. These compounds are high boiling PAHs, and it is assumed that comparison between the LML-method and the method used in this study is valid. The LML-PAHs values of the validated year 2024 are used for the comparison with the PAHs values found in this study. For reasons of representativeness, only the months of January, February and December of 2024 are used for the comparison, as the samples from this study were taken in comparable months. The average of the 24-hour PAHs measurements at the three LML-locations for 2024 is given in table 4. The maximum reported 24-hour PAHs measurements at the three LML-locations for 2024 are given in table 5. The average of the PAHs measurements of this study is given in table 4. The maximum reported PAHs values of this study are given in table 5.

PAH (24 hours average)	Unit	De Zilk (10444)	Schiedamse Vest (10418)	Wijk aan Zee (49553)	This study
Observations	N	41	38	42	16
Benzo[a]Pyrene	ng/m ³	0.04	0.06	0.28	0.44
Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene	ng/m ³	0.02	0.02	0.14	1.05

Table 4: Average of 24-hour PAHs measurements at three LML-locations and this study

PAH (maximum 24-hours value)	Unit	De Zilk (10444)	Schiedamse Vest (10418)	Wijk aan Zee (49553)	This study
Observations	N	41	38	42	16
Benzo[a]Pyrene	ng/m ³	0.14	0.14	0.76	1.27
Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene	ng/m ³	0.04	0.05	0.31	5.22

Table 5: Maximum reported PAHs values at the three LML-locations and this study

The number of measurements in this study is less than the number of measurements performed at the LML locations. Nevertheless, the average value and the maximum reported value for the individual PAHs in this study are higher than the values of the LML measurements.

For the strong carcinogenic Benzo[a]Pyrene, the average value of this study (0.44 ng/m³) is 1.5 times higher than the average value reported for LML location Wijk aan Zee (0.28 ng/m³). Also, the maximum value for Benzo[a]Pyrene reported in this study (1.27 ng/m³) is 1.7 times higher than the maximum value reported for LML location Wijk aan Zee (0.76 ng/m³).

For the 2.4 times stronger carcinogenic Dibenz[ah]Anthracene, the average value of this study (1.05 ng/m³) is 7.5 times higher than the average value reported for LML location Wijk aan Zee (0.14 ng/m³). Also, the maximum value for Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene reported in this study (5.22 ng/m³) is 17 times higher than the maximum value reported for LML location Wijk aan Zee (0.31 ng/m³).

A closer look at the data for the whole year 2024 for Benzo[a]Pyrene and Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene of the three LML locations shows a seasonal effect with the highest values reported for the months November till April. This effect is visible for all LML locations, but the most dominant for Wijk aan Zee. A plausible explanation for the seasonal effect is private wood burning. This is especially the case for LML location Wijk aan Zee, because this location is nearby residential areas situated in southwest to west directions. It is assumed, that the emission of PAHs by Tata Steel does not show a seasonal effect. The higher values for Wijk aan Zee in September till the 15th of October are presumably caused by Tata Steel, because in that time of the year the impact of private wood burning is less. The data for Benzo[a]Pyrene and Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene reported for the three LML locations for the whole year 2024 is given in figure 7.

Figure 7: Benzo[a]Pyrene & Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene measurements at three LML locations in 2024

Besides the breakdown of the absolute PAH concentrations, it is also interesting to investigate the breakdown of the relative PAH concentrations. For all sampling locations, the relative breakdown of the total PAHs concentrations into the individual PAH components is given in figure 8. The relative PAH concentration is calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{PAH relative (\%)} = \text{PAH concentration (ng/m}^3\text{)} * 100 / \text{PAHs total concentration (ng/m}^3\text{)}$$

By use of the relative breakdown of the total PAHs concentrations, the patterns among different sampling locations can be compared more accurate.

Figure 8: Relative PAHs breakdown for all sampling locations

At last, the average relative concentration of all individual PAH components among all sampling locations is given in figure 9. The sum of all relative concentrations in figure 9 makes a total of 100%.

Figure 9: Average relative contribution to PAHs total

The following observations can be derived from figure 8 & 9:

1. Naphthalene shows the highest contribution in the relative PAHs breakdown with an average of 22.3%
2. Fluorene shows the second highest contribution in the relative PAHs breakdown with an average of 11.3%.
3. The other PAH-components show a variable contribution in the relative PAHs breakdown with an average <10%.
4. Benzo[a]Anthracene and Chrysene show the lowest contribution in the relative PAHs breakdown with an average of 0.3%.
5. Conformity in the relative PAHs breakdown is clearly visible among different sampling locations like: Ameide & Ede, Barneveld & Schoorl1, Schoorl2 & Sneek2, Groet2 & Vlissingen. An explanation for this conformity could be similarity in the type of wood and/or burning conditions.

4.3 Wood smoke events

A method to define the existence of wood smoke in air can be derived from the PM2.5 measurements. Information about the reported total PAHs concentrations and measured PM2.5 concentrations inclusive the PM2.5 peak values are given in table 6. The PM2.5 data are indicative values. Besides woodsmoke, also other sources can emit PM2.5 like traffic.

The PM2.5 concentration is the average value calculated for the total PAHs sampling period, where the calculation is based on minute values. The PM2.5 peak value is the maximum averaged minute value measured during the PAHs sampling period. The highest average PM2.5 values are measured for Sneek experiment 1 and 2 and this location shows also the highest PM2.5 peak values of respectively 1804 µg/m³ and 922 µg/m³. Peak values of this level are extraordinarily high. It is therefore not surprising that this location shows also the highest PAHs values.

Sampling location	Experiment number	Total PAHs (ng/m ³)	PM2.5 (µg/m ³)	PM2.5 peak value(µg/m ³)
Ameide	1	26.1	30	124
Barneveld	1	8.1	5	61
Ede	1	14.7	13	309
Groet	1	5.3	29	58
	2	10.1	67	179
Middelburg	1	0.5	2	17
	2	4.8	3	28
Purmerend	1	1.9	55	102
Schoorl	1	9.7	33	64
	2	62.9	60	302
's-Gravenpolder	1	5.1	32	74
	2	5.4	5	91
	3	2.6	5	137
Sneek	1	176.7	118	1804
	2	122.9	83	922
Vlissingen	1	35.6	54	91
Warmenhuizen	1	12.1	12	105

Table 6: Average PAHs- and PM2.5 concentrations inclusive PM2.5 peak values

The presence of close by wood smoke is measured as sudden high peak values on the baseline of the PM2.5 background level. This effect is visible in the PM2.5 sensor graphs and are given in section 4.5. It must be noted that PM2.5 originated from wood smoke on longer distances is part of the background level.

Based on the results of table 2 (average windspeed) and table 6 (total PAHs), it is investigated if there is a correlation between average windspeed en PAHs concentration. The coherence is very weak, resulting in a correlation coefficient of 0.105. One would expect that higher wind speeds would lead to higher dilution of the PAH concentration. However, due to local wind effects, such as the downdraft effect, a higher PAH concentration can even occur at higher wind speeds. The highest concentration of Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene in Vlissingen (5.22 ng/m³, table 5) is measured with an average windspeed of 4 Bft. A high wind speed does not guarantee good air quality.

The exposure to PAHs can be much higher during wood smoke events. Higher exposure can lead to acceleration of health effects. During wood smoke events one should better close the windows and vents to prevent exposure to PAHs within the house. Even when there is no wood smoke from close by wood stoves, PAHs originated from wood stoves on longer distances could still be present in the background.

4.4 Semi Volatile Organic Compounds

As mentioned in section 2.3 one of the sampling tubes is analysed for the existence of SVOC's. It was chosen to take the sampling tube from Schoorl experiment 2. The total PAHs concentration for this location is 62.9 ng/m³ and all the 16 EPA-PAHs are reported. The concentration of the 10 most abundant SVOC-components is listed in table 7. The reported concentrations of the SVOC's are a factor 40 to 400 higher than the total PAHs concentration. The concentrations of the SVOC's are calculated by use of the response factor of Naphthalene.

Most of the listed components in table 7 are irritating for eyes and lungs. 2,5-Cyclohexadiene-1,4-dione, 2,5-diphenyl- shows the highest concentration and has strong irritating properties and can cause asthma symptoms. It should be noted just 10 SVOC's are reported. To get more insight into the composition of all SVOC's it is recommended to analyze more sampling tubes. Besides the 16 EPA-PAHs and 10 most abundant components, it is recommended to analyze the full scope of remaining PAH derivatives and SVOC's. In this way more information will become available about the toxic properties of wood smoke.

Component	CAS number	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) #
2,5-Cyclohexadiene-1,4-dione, 2,5-diphenyl-	844-51-9	25.1
5-Octen-2-one, 6-methyl-8-(2,6,6-trimethyl-1-cyclohexen-1-yl)-	55638-41-0	7.6
Benzoic acid	65-85-0	5.9
O-Methoxy-alpha-methylbenzyl alcohol	13513-82-1	4.0
Phenylmaleic anhydride	36122-35-7	3.4
9H-Fluorene, 9-methylene-	4425-82-5	3.2
Hexadecanoic acid	57-10-3	3.1
2-Hydroxy-4-methylbenzoic acid	50-85-1	3.0
Squalene	111-02-4	2.8
3,7,11-Tridecatricenoic acid, 4,8,12-trimethyl-, methyl ester, (Z,E)-	36237-70-4	2.4

Table 7: SVOC's reported for sampling location Schoorl experiment 2

: Concentration as Naphthalene Equivalent in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
 CAS number : Chemical Abstracts Service number

4.5 PAHs breakdown per sampling location

In this section the PAHs breakdown for every sampling location is discussed. The graphs for PM2.5 and meteorology are generated by Scapeler²³. The PAHs breakdown is in ng/m^3 .

As a discrimination criterium, the concentration of PAHs is divided into four classes:

1. Low : $\leq 1 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$
2. Moderate : $< 1 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3 \text{ PAHs} \leq 10 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$
3. High : $< 10 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3 \text{ PAHs} \leq 100 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$
4. Extreme : $> 100 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$

The presence of wood smoke during the sampling time is based on the data of the PM2.5 measurements.

23 <https://www.scapeler.com/>

4.5.1 Ameide

Sampling time: 12-JAN-25 12:10 till 13-JAN-25 15:05.

During the measurement in Ameide the weather was sunny and cold with high humidity. The wind was variable and weak in the beginning, but on the 13th of January the wind increased from south directions.

Wood smoke was present for 60% of the time.

The concentration of Naphthalene is remarkably high compared to the other PAHs. In general, the other PAHs are low in concentration.

4.5.2 Barneveld

Sampling time: 26-JAN-25 13:10 till 27-JAN-25 13:10.

During the measurement in Barneveld the weather was windy with partly sun and rain. The temperature was high for this time of the year. The wind was quite strong from southeast tot southwest directions.

Wood smoke was present for 60% of the time.

The concentration of PAHs is moderate to low.

4.5.3 Ede

Sampling time: 25-JAN-25 12:38 till 26-JAN-25 14:10.

During the measurement in Ede the weather was calm and cold with partly sun and some rain. The humidity was high. The wind was variable from all directions.

Wood smoke was present for 50% of the time. During the night of 26 January wood smoke was present between 2AM till 3:30AM.

The concentration of Naphthalene is remarkably high compared to the other PAHs. The other PAHs are low in concentration.

4.5.4 Groet

Sampling time:

1. Measurement 1: 7-FEB-25 10:00 till 8-FEB-25 10:00
2. Measurement 2: 19-FEB-25 09:00 till 20-FEB-25 11:00

During measurement 1 the weather in Groet was very cold with strong wind from easterly directions. The humidity was between 70% and 85%. During measurement 2 it was windy and cold with a southeast wind. The humidity was between 50% and 90%.

Nearby wood smoke was temporarily present during one hour on the 7th of February (4% of the time), but on the 19th of February wood smoke was dominant till 2AM on the 20th of February (65% of the time).

The concentration of PAHs is low to moderate for both measurements, but for measurement 2 the concentrations are higher, and more PAHs are reported.

The concentration of PAHs for measurement 2 is not much higher than measurement 1, while wood smoke was dominant present during measurement 2.

4.5.5 Middelburg

Sampling time:

1. Measurement 1: 22-DEC-24 10:50 till 23-DEC-24 07:00
2. Measurement 2: 22-DEC-24 11:01 till 23-DEC-24 07:00

Both measurements were performed on the same days. During the measurements in Middelburg the weather was mild and windy with periods of rain, and the wind came from west to northwest directions. The humidity was between 65% and 85%.

Measurement 1 (Middelburg_Zuidzijde_227665) is considered as the blank in this study. The setup of this Tenax tube was free from wood smoke. The air was clear and bright and the PM2.5 level of the background was very low with a concentration < 5 µg/m³. During the measurement just one small PM2.5 signal was observed (8:30 PM; blue curve in PM2.5 graphic).

During measurement 2 (Middelburg_Noordzijde_227663) wood smoke was present for 60% of the time (light green curve in PM2.5 graphic)

The concentration of PAHs is low for measurement 1 and just two PAHs are reported. For measurement 2 the concentrations are also low, but more PAHs are reported. The strong winds have impact on the dilution of wood smoke and hence impact on the PAHs concentration too.

4.5.6 Nunspeet

Unfortunately, the analysis of the sampling tubes from Nunspeet was not successful. The PAHs concentrations are not known. For reference, the graphs for PM2.5 and Meteorology are given below.

4.5.7 Purmerend

Sampling time: 13-JAN-25 17:35 till 14-JAN-25 20:35.

During the measurement in Purmerend the weather was calm and cold on the 13th of January, but more wind and milder on the 14th of January. The humidity was high and between 85% and 95%. The wind was moderate from southwest directions.

Wood smoke was present for 45% of the time.

The concentration of the PAHs is low.

4.5.8 Schoorl

Sampling time:

1. Measurement 1: 16-JAN-25 14:37 till 17-JAN-25 15:00
2. Measurement 2: 21-JAN-25 20:25 till 22-JAN-25 21:40

Measurement 1 (Schoorl1_227662) was performed at the front side of the house. The PM2.5 registration at the front side of the house is presented by the red curve and at the back side of the house by the blue curve. The weather in Schoorl was cold with very high humidity and foggy conditions. The wind was calm from south directions. The PM2.5 registration shows that the presence of wood smoke was low at the front side of the house but was clearly present at the back side of the house for 30% of the time.

Measurement 2 (Schoorl2_227661) was performed at the the back side of the house. The weather in Schoorl was cold with high humidity and partly foggy conditions. The wind was calm from south to southeast directions. The PM2.5 registration at the back side of the house shows wood smoke was present for 35% of the time.

The concentration of PAHs is low to moderate for measurement 1. For measurement 2 the concentrations are moderate to high with two PAHs > 10 ng/m³. For measurement 2 all 16 EPA-PAHs are reported, but also the highest reported value for Benzo[a]Pyrene (1.27 ng/m³).

4.5.9 's-Gravenpolder

Sampling time:

1. Measurement 1: 01-DEC-24 10:00 till 02-DEC-24 00:30
2. Measurement 2: 03-DEC-24 09:43 till 03-DEC-24 23:30
3. Measurement 3: 02-JAN-25 17:05 till 03-JAN-25 08:15

During measurement 1 the weather in 's-Gravenpolder was mild with high humidity between 70% and 90%. The wind was moderate from south directions. The PM2.5 registration (light purple curve PMS_D3B5 in all PM2.5 graphics) shows that the presence of wood smoke was on a low level between 3PM and 01AM, for 70% of the time.

During measurement 2 the weather in 's-Gravenpolder was mild with high humidity between 70% and 95%. The wind was calm from southwest to northwest directions. The PM2.5 registration shows presence of wood smoke between 5:30PM and 02:30AM, for 50% of the time.

During measurement 3 the weather in 's-Gravenpolder was cold with high humidity around 85%. The wind was calm to moderate from northwest directions. The PM2.5 registration shows presence of wood smoke between 5PM and 11PM, for 40% of the time.

The concentration of PAHs is low to moderate for measurements 1 and 2 and low for measurement 3.

4.5.10 Sneek

Sampling time:

1. Measurement 1: 17-JAN-25 19:22 till 18-JAN-25 19:35
2. Measurement 2: 20-JAN-25 19:00 till 21-JAN-25 19:00

During both measurements in Sneek, the weather was freezing cold with very high humidity. There was fog on the 17th and 18th of January. The wind was calm during both measurements from southeast to south directions. During both measurements the wood smoke was dominantly present for approximately 75% of the time. The PM2.5 values were extremely high with peak values far above 250 µg/m³.

The concentration of PAHs shows a broad range from low to extreme for measurement 1 (Sneek1_227671) and moderate to high for measurement 2 (Sneek2_171092). It is remarkable, Acenaphthene is not reported for measurement 1 while it was high for measurement 2. This looks to be related to a possible analysis issue. During both measurements the wood smoke came from the same wood stoves.

4.5.11 Vlissingen

Sampling time: 19-FEB-25 08:52 till 20-FEB-25 10:30

During the measurement in Vlissingen, the weather was cold to mild with moderate humidity between 60% and 95%. The wind was calm to moderate from southeast to south directions. Wood smoke was present for 50% of the time.

The concentration of PAHs is low to high. The PAHs breakdown profile distinguishes from all other profiles by the presence of the 4 lightest PAHs and the 4 heaviest PAHs.

ApriSensor Vlissingen (ECB3)

KNMI station 06310 Vlissingen

4.5.12 Warmenhuizen

Sampling time: 30-JAN-25 19:00 till 31-JAN-25 22:30

During the measurement in Warmenhuizen, the weather was cold to mild with high humidity between 80% and 95%. The wind was calm from west to south directions. Wood smoke was present for 55% of the time. Significantly more wood smoke was present after 6PM on the 31st of January when the wind changed from southwest to southeast.

The concentration of PAHs is low to moderate.

4.5.13 Zoetermeer

Unfortunately, the analysis of the sampling tube from Zoetermeer was not successful. The PAHs concentrations are not known. For reference, the graphs for PM2.5 and Meteorology are given below.

5 Conclusions and Recommendations

This study investigated the (hyper)local human exposure to PAHs in the outside air, emitted by nearby wood fired appliances in the living environment. During the winter season from 2024 to 2025, a total of 17 successful measurements of 16 Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (16 EPA-PAHs) in the outside air were conducted at 13 different locations in the Netherlands.

In general, a great variety in PAHs concentrations, but also in the PAHs compositions is observed among the 13 sampling locations. The highest concentrations of total PAHs were measured in Sneek, respectively 177 ng/m³ and 123 ng/m³ on two different days. This location is highly exposed to wood smoke resulting in regularly very high PM_{2.5} peak values far above 250 µg/m³. The lowest concentration of 0.5 ng/m³ total PAHs is measured in Middelburg and is considered as the background concentration of 'clean air'. The highest concentration of an individual PAH is observed for Naphthalene in Sneek with a value of 119.6 ng/m³. In general, Naphthalene shows also the highest average relative contribution to the total PAHs concentration with a value of 22.3%, followed by Fluorene with 11.3% and Anthracene with 9.0%. Naphthalene is considered by the IARC as possibly carcinogenic to humans.

The reported concentration of the carcinogenic Benzo[a]Pyrene varies between <0.1 ng/m³ in Middelburg Zuidzijde and 1.27 ng/m³ in Schoorl. The average value of Benzo[a]Pyrene is 0.44 ng/m³ (16 measurements) and is 1.5 times higher than the average value for the winter season reported for a location of the Dutch national air quality monitoring network in Wijk aan Zee (0.28 ng/m³, 2024, 42 measurements). The location in Wijk aan Zee is 1 to 1,5 km north from the large industrial complex Tata Steel. Tata Steel is known for its PAH emissions into the environment. The maximum value for Benzo[a]Pyrene reported in this study (Schoorl, 1.27 ng/m³) is 1.7 times higher than the maximum value reported for Wijk aan Zee (0.76 ng/m³).

The reported concentration of Dibenz[ah]Anthracene, which is 2.4 times more carcinogenic than Benzo[a]Pyrene, varies between <0.1 ng/m³ in Middelburg Zuidzijde and 5.22 ng/m³ in Vlissingen. The average value of Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene is 1.05 ng/m³ (16 measurements) and is 7.5 times higher than the average value for the winter season reported for Wijk aan Zee (0.14 ng/m³, 2024, 42 measurements). The maximum value for Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene reported in this study (Vlissingen, 5.22 ng/m³) is 17 times higher than the maximum value reported for location Wijk aan Zee (0.31 ng/m³). Investigation of the reported LML data for the whole year 2024 shows a seasonal effect with the highest values for November till April. The most obvious explanation for the seasonal effect would be private wood burning in residential areas in southwest and west directions.

This study did not show a clear relation between windspeed and PAHs concentration. Based on 17 measurements, the correlation coefficient is 0.105. One would expect that higher wind speeds would lead to higher dilution of the PAH concentration. However, due to local wind effects, such as the downdraft effect, a higher PAH concentration can even occur at higher wind speeds. The highest concentration of Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene in Vlissingen (5.22 ng/m³) is measured with an average windspeed of 4 Bft. A high wind speed does not guarantee good air quality.

One measurement at Schoorl is subjected to both the analysis of the 16 EPA-PAHs but also the analysis of 10 of the most abundant Semi Volatile Organic Components (SVOC). The reported concentrations of the SVOC's are a factor 40 to 400 higher than the total PAHs concentration. The highest concentration of 25.1 µg/m³ is reported for 2,5-Cyclohexadiene-1,4-dione, 2,5-diphenyl-, a strong irritant quinone and can cause asthma symptoms.

To get more insight into the composition of all SVOC's and the non-EPA-PAHs (derivates), it is recommended to analyze more sampling tubes. Besides the 16 EPA-PAHs and 10 most abundant components, it is strongly recommended to analyze the full scope of the remaining PAH derivates and SVOC's with specific focus on the oxidized PAHs. In this way more information will become available about the toxic and carcinogenic properties of wood smoke.

Based on the results of this study, the concentration of the 16 EPA-PAHs in the outside air can reach a level of 350 times the background concentration of clean air if active wood burning appliances are nearby. The concentration of Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene is for 50% of the measurements more than twice the concentration of Benzo[a]Pyrene. Although Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene is 2.4 times as carcinogenic as Benzo[a]Pyrene, Dibenz[a,h]Anthracene does not need to be registered under the 4 PRTR-PAHs in the EU and is not included in exceedances of the PAH standard. However, the US Department of Public Health and the US-EPA recommend considering the equivalent effects of other carcinogenic PAHs when calculating cancer risks. More research is requested, including into the interactions that occur within the different PAH mixtures. German- and American research showed that non carcinogenic low molecular weight PAHs can enhance the carcinogenicity of high molecular weight PAHs. Reference is also made to German research in which, of the 59 PAHs measured, the 43 non-EPA PAHs were found to be responsible for 69% to 95% of the carcinogenicity. Recent research shows that the 16 EPA-PAHs appear to represent only 1% of all PAH-derivatives that are formed during combustion processes, mainly from wood and coal. The other 99% are equally toxic and 13 times more carcinogenic than Benzo[a]Pyrene at equal mass concentrations.

Therefore, the WHO warns that the current annual limit of 0.12 ng/m³ Benzo[a]Pyrene probably does not provide sufficient protection to humans. The WHO indicates that for carcinogenic PAHs there is no threshold, so the lowest possible exposure should be aimed. According to the WHO the limit was calculated for the risk of lung cancer, not for all other types of cancer that can develop and not for the oxidative effects from PAHs such as cardiorespiratory diseases and developmental and behavioral disorders in children. Therefore, with respect for our health, both the WHO-limit (0.12 ng/m³) and EU-limit (1 ng/m³) looks to be outdated. In particular, the impact of wood burning is underestimated. According to European research, the oxidized PAH mixtures from private wood burning appear to be the main source of the oxidative potential of PM_{2.5} in Europe. The oxidative stress and (resulting) inflammatory reactions explain the cellular and DNA damage observed with PM_{2.5}.

In many locations, wood is daily used as fuel to heat houses for a significant part of the year. It must be clearly understood that residential wood burning will cause a significant increase of the human exposure to PAHs in the outside air. This can lead to increased risk of human health damage. There is no safe threshold value below which no health damage occurs.

Recent British research conducted by the Ricardo group has shown that modern ECO-design wood stoves emit more PAHs and black carbon than old types of wood stoves and fireplaces. In the UK, the Ricardo report has had far-reaching consequences. The English Advertising Standards Authority ([ASA](#)) has urged the English stove industry to stop advertising that modern ECO-design stoves significantly reduce harmful emissions. Let this be a valuable lesson in raising awareness that burning wood can never be clean and that the emissions have a huge impact on the local air quality. Good air quality is vital for our health, nature and climate.

Phasing out private wood burning should therefore be high on the political agenda.

6 Conclusies en Aanbevelingen

Deze studie onderzocht de (hyper)lokale blootstelling van mensen aan PAK's in de buitenlucht, afkomstig van nabijgelegen op hout gestookte toestellen in de woonomgeving. Gedurende het winterseizoen van 2024 tot 2025 werden in totaal 17 succesvolle metingen verricht van 16 polycyclische aromatische koolwaterstoffen (16 EPA-PAK's) in de buitenlucht op 13 verschillende locaties in Nederland.

Over het algemeen is een grote variatie in PAK-concentraties waargenomen, ook in de samenstelling van de PAK's tussen de 13 meetlocaties. De hoogste concentraties totale PAK's werden op twee verschillende dagen gemeten in Sneek, respectievelijk 177 ng/m³ en 123 ng/m³. De meetlocatie in Sneek is sterk blootgesteld aan houtrook, wat resulteert in regelmatig zeer hoge PM_{2.5}-piekconcentraties van ruim boven de 250 µg/m³. De laagste concentratie totale PAK's van 0.5 ng/m³ werd gemeten op de meetlocatie in Middelburg en wordt beschouwd als de achtergrondconcentratie van 'schone lucht'. De hoogste concentratie van een individuele PAK werd gemeten voor Naftaleen in Sneek met een concentratie van 119.6 ng/m³. Over het algemeen vertoont Naftaleen ook de hoogste gemiddelde relatieve bijdrage aan de totale PAK-concentratie met een waarde van 22.3%, gevolgd door Fluoreen met 11.3% en Antraceen met 9.0%. Naftaleen wordt door het IARC beschouwd als mogelijk kankerverwekkend voor de mens.

De gemeten concentratie van de kankerverwekkende stof Benzo[a]Pyreen varieert tussen <0.1 ng/m³ in Middelburg Zuidzijde en 1.27 ng/m³ in Schoorl. De gemiddelde concentratie van Benzo[a]Pyreen is 0.44 ng/m³ (16 metingen) en is 1.5 keer hoger dan de gemiddelde concentratie voor het winterseizoen die is gerapporteerd voor een locatie van het Nederlandse nationale luchtkwaliteitsmeetnetwerk (LML) in Wijk aan Zee (0.28 ng/m³, 2024, 42 metingen). De LML-locatie in Wijk aan Zee ligt 1 tot 1.5 km ten noorden van het grote industriële complex Tata Steel. Tata Steel staat bekend om de uitstoot van PAK's in het milieu. De maximale concentratie van 1.27 ng/m³ voor Benzo[a]Pyreen die in dit onderzoek in Schoorl is gemeten, is 1.7 keer hoger dan de maximale concentratie van 0.76 ng/m³ die voor locatie Wijk aan Zee is gerapporteerd.

De gemeten concentratie van Dibenz[a,h]Antraceen, dat 2.4 keer meer kankerverwekkend is dan Benzo[a]Pyreen, varieert tussen <0.1 ng/m³ in Middelburg Zuidzijde en 5.22 ng/m³ in Vlissingen. De gemiddelde concentratie van Dibenz[a,h]Antraceen is 1.05 ng/m³ (16 metingen) en is 7.5 keer hoger dan de gemiddelde concentratie voor het winterseizoen die is gerapporteerd voor de LML-locatie Wijk aan Zee (0.14 ng/m³, 2024, 42 metingen). De maximale concentratie van 5.22 ng/m³ voor Dibenz[a,h]Antraceen die in deze studie is gemeten in Vlissingen, is 17 keer hoger dan de maximale concentratie van 0.31 ng/m³ die is gerapporteerd voor de locatie Wijk aan Zee. Onderzoek van de gerapporteerde LML-gegevens voor het gehele jaar 2024 toont een seizoen effect aan met de hoogste concentraties van november tot en met april. De meest voor de hand liggende verklaring voor het seizoen effect is het stoken van hout in woonwijken gelegen in zuidwestelijke en westelijke richtingen.

Deze studie heeft geen duidelijk verband aangetoond tussen windsnelheid en PAK-concentratie. Op basis van 17 metingen is de correlatiecoëfficiënt 0.105. Men zou verwachten dat een hogere windsnelheid zou leiden tot een grotere verdunning van de PAK-concentratie. Door lokale windeffecten, zoals het downdraft effect, kan zelfs bij hogere windsnelheden een hoge PAK-concentratie voorkomen. De hoogste concentratie Dibenz[a,h]Antraceen in Vlissingen (5.22 ng/m³) werd gemeten bij een gemiddelde windsnelheid van 4 Beaufort. Een hoge windsnelheid garandeert dus geen goede luchtkwaliteit.

Eén meting in Schoorl werd uitgevoerd voor zowel de analyse van de 16 EPA-PAK's als de analyse van 10 van de meest voorkomende semi-vluchtige organische componenten (SVOC's). De gemeten concentraties van de SVOC's zijn een factor 40 tot 400 hoger dan de totale PAK-concentratie. De hoogste concentratie van 25.1 µg/m³ werd gemeten voor 2,5-cyclohexadien-1,4-dion, 2,5-difenyl-, een sterk irriterende chinon die astmaklachten kan veroorzaken.

Om meer inzicht te krijgen in de samenstelling van alle SVOC's en de niet-EPA-PAK's (derivaten), wordt aanbevolen om meer monsterbuizen te analyseren. Naast de 16 EPA-PAK's en de 10 meest voorkomende SVOC-componenten, wordt sterk aanbevolen om het volledige spectrum van de overige SVOC's en PAK-derivaten te analyseren, met specifieke aandacht voor de geoxideerde PAK's. Op deze manier zal meer informatie beschikbaar komen over de toxische en kankerverwekkende eigenschappen van houtrook.

Op basis van de resultaten van dit onderzoek kan de concentratie van de 16 EPA-PAK's in de buitenlucht oplopen tot 350 keer de achtergrondconcentratie van schone lucht als er actieve houtkachels in de buurt zijn. De concentratie Dibenz[a,h]Antraceen is bij 50% van de metingen meer dan twee keer zo hoog als de concentratie Benzo[a]Pyreen. Hoewel Dibenz[a,h]Antraceen 2.4 keer meer kankerverwekkend is dan Benzo[a]Pyreen, hoeft Dibenz[a,h]Antraceen niet te worden geregistreerd onder de 4 PRTR-PAK's in de EU en wordt het niet meegerekend bij overschrijdingen van de PAK-norm. Het Amerikaanse ministerie van Volksgezondheid en de Amerikaanse EPA adviseren echter om bij het berekenen van kankerrisico's wel rekening te houden met de equivalente effecten van andere kankerverwekkende PAK's. Meer onderzoek is nodig, onder meer naar de interacties die optreden binnen de verschillende PAK-mengsels. Onderzoek laat namelijk zien dat niet-kankerverwekkende PAK's met een laagmoleculair gewicht de kankerverwekkende werking van PAK's met een hoogmoleculair gewicht kunnen versterken. Er wordt ook verwezen naar Duits onderzoek waarin van de 59 gemeten PAK's de 43 niet-EPA-PAK's verantwoordelijk bleken te zijn voor 69% tot 95% van de kankerverwekkende werking. Recent onderzoek laat zien dat de 16 EPA-PAK's slechts 1% vertegenwoordigen van alle PAK-derivaten die tijdens verbrandingsprocessen ontstaan, van voornamelijk hout en steenkool. De overige 99% zijn even toxisch en 13 keer zo kankerverwekkend als Benzo[a]Pyreen bij dezelfde massa concentraties.

De WHO waarschuwde al eerder dat de huidige WHO-limiet met 0.12 ng/m³ Benzo[a]Pyreen als indicatorstof waarschijnlijk onvoldoende bescherming biedt. Volgens de WHO bestaat er voor de kankerverwekkende PAK's geen drempelwaarde en moet er dus worden gestreefd naar de laagst mogelijke blootstelling. Daarnaast geeft de WHO aan dat de WHO-limiet is berekend op basis van het risico op longkanker, niet op alle andere vormen van kanker die ook kunnen ontstaan en ook niet op de oxidatieve effecten van PAK's zoals hart- en vaatziekten, longaandoeningen en ontwikkelings- en gedragsstoornissen bij kinderen. Met het oog op onze gezondheid lijken dus zowel de WHO-limiet als de EU-limiet (1 ng/m³) achterhaald. Met name wordt de impact van particuliere houtstook onderschat. Volgens Europese wetenschappers zijn namelijk de geoxideerde PAK-mengsels uit particuliere houtstook de belangrijkste bron van het oxidatieve potentieel in het PM2.5 in Europa. De veroorzaakt oxidatieve stress met ontstekingsreacties brengt schade toe aan afweer- en weefselcellen en aan DNA zoals die wordt gezien als gevolg van PM2.5.

In veel dorpen en steden wordt hout dagelijks gebruikt als brandstof om huizen te verwarmen gedurende een aanzienlijk deel van het jaar. Het is van groot belang te realiseren dat het stoken van hout in woningen de blootstelling van de mens aan PAK's in de buitenlucht aanzienlijk doet toenemen. Dit leidt tot een verhoogd risico op gezondheidsschade.

Recent Brits onderzoek van de Ricardo-groep heeft aangetoond dat moderne ECO-design houtkachels meer PAK's en black carbon (roet) uitstoten dan oude typen houtkachels en open haarden. In het Verenigd Koninkrijk heeft het Ricardo-rapport verstrekkende gevolgen gehad. De Engelse reclameautoriteit (ASA) heeft de Engelse kachelindustrie (SIA) opgeroepen te stoppen met het uiten van reclame dat moderne ECO-design houtkachels de schadelijke uitstoot aanzienlijk verminderen. Laat dit een waardevolle les zijn om het bewustzijn te vergroten dat het stoken van hout nooit schoon kan zijn en dat de uitstoot een enorme impact heeft op de lokale luchtkwaliteit. Een goede luchtkwaliteit is essentieel voor onze gezondheid, de natuur en het klimaat.

Uitfasering van particuliere houtstook zou daarom hoog op de politieke agenda moeten staan.

Appendix 1

PAHs measurement form

Sampling site information										
Sampling location						Sampling period				
	Description:					From:				
indoor						To:				
outdoor										
Are there photos from the sampling location:						Yes / No				
Active sampling information:										
	Pump ID:		Start sampling			Stop sampling				
PDMS / Tenax			date/time:				date/time:			
	Tube No		Sampling flow		ml/min	Sampling flow		ml/min		

Appendix 2

Primary PAHs data reported by VITO.

Sampling location_Tube nr	1_Naphthalene	2_Acenaphthylene	3_Acenaphthene	4_Fluorene	5_Phenanthrene	6_Anthracene	7_Fluoranthene	8_Pyrene	9_Benzo(a)anthracene	10_Chrysene	11_Benzo(b)fluoranthene	12_Benzo(k)fluoranthene	13_Benzo(a)pyrene	14_Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	15_Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene	16_Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	Total PAH
	ng/m ³	ng/m ³	ng/m ³	ng/m ³	ng/m ³	ng/m ³	ng/m ³	ng/m ³	ng/m ³								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	
Middelburg Noordzijde_227663	< LOD	< LOD	0.46	0.40	0.30	0.35	0.51	0.32	< LOD	< LOD	1.01	0.45	0.43	< LOD	0.44	0.14	4.8
s-Gravenpolder 1_227674	1.38	< LOD	< LOD	0.48	0.70	0.70	0.63	0.28	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	0.50	0.38	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	5.1
s-Gravenpolder 2_227673	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	0.85	1.06	1.06	0.60	0.30	< LOD	< LOD	1.04	0.45	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	5.4
Middelburg Zuidzijde_227665	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	0.18	0.02	0.04	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	0.24	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	0.5
s-Gravenpolder 3_171100	0.55	< LOD	< LOD	0.33	0.46	0.44	0.14	0.36	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	0.31	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	2.6
Sneek 2_171092	71.40	2.50	11.66	3.72	5.84	5.80	4.20	3.14	1.24	1.22	2.29	1.15	1.24	2.88	3.20	1.44	122.9
Barneveld_171096	< LOD	0.23	< LOD	0.80	1.06	1.03	1.18	0.83	< LOD	< LOD	0.81	0.40	0.34	0.43	0.72	0.23	8.1
Ameide_171098	19.80	< LOD	< LOD	1.54	0.83	0.89	0.97	0.79	< LOD	< LOD	0.55	0.30	0.28	< LOD	0.11	< LOD	26.1
Ede_227685	10.70	< LOD	< LOD	0.66	0.52	0.54	0.70	0.62	< LOD	< LOD	0.46	0.26	0.22	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	14.7
Sneek 1_227671	119.60	4.51	< LOD	8.51	12.84	11.96	8.26	4.37	1.64	1.59	1.51	0.77	0.88	0.29	< LOD	< LOD	176.7
Schoorl 2_227661	10.60	2.18	11.55	4.26	5.80	5.98	4.36	3.18	1.27	1.25	2.24	1.20	1.27	2.92	3.40	1.48	62.9
Schoorl 1_227662	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	1.01	1.37	1.29	1.37	0.90	0.13	0.14	0.80	0.47	0.38	0.73	0.77	0.32	9.7
Warmenhuizen_171091	3.50	< LOD	< LOD	1.89	1.24	1.17	1.41	0.95	< LOD	< LOD	0.61	0.39	0.24	0.37	0.16	0.15	12.1
Purmerend_171093	< LOD	0.12	0.40	0.44	< LOD	< LOD	0.36	0.26	0.14	0.17	< LOD	< LOD	1.9				
Groet 1_171094 #	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	1.30	0.60	0.60	< LOD	0.20	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	0.27	0.96	0.76	0.56	5.3
Groet 2_227670 #	0.67	1.66	< LOD	1.37	0.43	0.43	< LOD	0.36	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	0.38	1.79	1.75	1.25	10.1
Vlissingen_227669 #	1.10	5.49	11.07	3.23	0.25	0.29	< LOD	0.52	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	0.83	4.64	5.22	2.98	35.6
Nunspeet 1_171095	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed								
Nunspeet 2_171097	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed								
Zoetermeer_227666	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed	failed								